

the entire crop at the seedling stage.

Recently a late-sown 1978 kharif crop of the variety Jaya was attacked after the heading stage. Small punctures

appeared in the middle of the flag leaf and its margin was sometimes discolored. On a few plants, the second and third leaves were also damaged. ■

Evaluation of insecticides for gall midge control

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Large strips of Ratna that had been transplanted on 3 August 1978 were

treated on 8 and 24 September with several insecticides and formulations.

At harvest observations were made on two 1- × 1-m plots in each treatment to determine the percentages of silver shoots and the yield (see table). Percent silver shoots was lowest and yield highest in the granular treatment of quinalphos. ■

Percentage of silver shoots and panicles, and yield of Ratna treated with various insecticides. Raipur, India, 1978.

Treatment	Dosage	Silver shoots (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Quinalphos 5G	1 kg a.i./ha	32.0	2.7
Phorate 10G	1 kg a.i./ha	36.0	2.0
Carbofuran 3G	1 kg a.i./ha	36.7	1.8
Malathion 50EC	0.05% concn	47.6	1.6
Sevimol 40EC	0.05% concn	41.0	2.0
Phosalone 35 EC	0.05% concn	48.3	1.9
Monocrotophos 40 EC	0.05% concn	56.8	1.8
Phosphamidon 100EC	0.05% concn	33.9	1.6
Quinalphos 30EC	0.05% concn	40.2	1.5
BHC 10% dust	25 kg/ha	41.4	1.5
Untreated control	—	69.0	1.5

^aCarbaryl in molasses.

Biological studies of the population dynamics of rice brown planthopper and green leafhopper

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The influence of weather factors on the field populations of rice brown planthopper (BPH) and green leafhopper (GLH) was studied.

GLH populations increased at both

higher maximum and minimum temperatures (see table). BPH populations decreased at both high temperatures and lower minimum temperatures. GLH populations were higher at lower humidity levels. but BPH populations were positively correlated with higher humidity. No direct relationship between the amount of rainfall and GLH incidence was found. But the BPH population peaked at no or low rainfall (6-10 mm) and declined when rainfall exceeded 10 mm.

Correlation between weather elements and the incidence of rice green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers, Annamalaiagar, India.^a

Weather element	Green leafhopper		Brown planthopper (short-term season)
	Short term (Jul-Sep)	2d season (Nov-Jan)	
Max temp	+0.7166**	+0.5030*	-0.8122**
Min temp	-0.6922**	-0.5021*	+0.9122**
Humidity	-0.7022**	-0.7790**	+0.5610**
Rainfall	0.0056 ns	1.1450 ns	-0.7101**
Sunshine	+0.6328*	+0.7516**	-0.6222**

^a* Significant at 5% level. ** Significant at 1% level. ns = not significant.

The GLH population was higher with more bright sunshine (3-8 hours) and decreased with fewer hours of sunshine. The BPH population increased with fewer bright-sunshine hours. ■

Rice leaf folder attacks in India

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The rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae), normally a minor rice pest, occurred in epidemic proportions in 1978 on upland, drilled autumn rice (aus) in Coochbehar and Jalpaiguri, two rice-growing districts of North Bengal, India. Most areas of maximum infestation were on the peripheral regions of forest reserves and on plains near the foothills of the sub-Himalayan ranges. In aus rice, which is generally sown in March or April and harvested in July or August, the infestation was first noticed in the last week of April; incidence peaked in the second week of May. The insect spread to about 22,000 ha. Where infestation was severe, the rice plants (almost entirely rainfed) withered completely. Coochbehar and Jalpaiguri receive an average annual precipitation of about 3,200 mm. Rainfall averages 50, 130, and 400 mm in March, April, and May. But in 1978, it averaged 3.2, 100.2, and 295 mm. The attack was confined mostly to the late-sown crop. But the infestation subsided with the onset of late May rains. ■

Performance of sprayers and influence of water volumes in insecticidal control of rice ear-cutting caterpillar

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A field experiment was conducted to test the performance of sprayers and the influence of water volumes in control of the rice ear-cutting caterpillar *Mythimna separata* Walk in paddy at Varansai in 1976-77. The ground sprayers evaluated were mist-blower, hand-compression, foot, and knapsack sprayers. The volumes

tested were 50, 75, and 100 liters/ha applied by the low-volume sprayer (mist blower), and 500, 750, and 1000 liters/ha with each high-volume sprayer (hand-compression, foot, and knapsack). For convenience, the volumes were categorized as low, medium, and high. The fixed dose of the insecticide, fenitrothion as Sumithion 500 E at 1.0 kg a.i./ha mixed in varying water volumes, was applied by each sprayer on 11 October 1976 at the grain-formation stage of the variety Saken. The 12

treatments and control were replicated 3 times in a factorial randomized design. Insecticide was applied only once.

Equal and uniform application of the insecticidal fluid was ensured by adjustment of the operator's speed and timing. At spraying time the larvae were at the 4th- to 5th-instar stage. The performance of sprayers and the influence of water volumes were evaluated on the basis of larvae reduction.

The hand-compression spray equipment was significantly superior in reduction of larvae (95%) compared with the mist-blower (56%). The lever-operated knapsack sprayer and the foot sprayer performed equally well in pest control. Low water volume gave 83% control and medium volume, 83%. The high-volume treatment gave 68% larvae reduction. The average effect of treatment combinations was significantly higher than that of the control. ■

Effectiveness of foliar spray insecticides in brown planthopper control in Thailand

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Six insecticides were tested in the 1977 dry season in central Thailand. The experiment was in a randomized complete

block design with 7 treatments and 4 replications. The 5- x 6-m² plots were planted to the variety RD1. Insecticides were applied by knapsack sprayers at a concentration of 0.1% active ingredient at 40, 50, and 70 days after transplanting. Brown planthopper (BPH) populations were collected by a D-vac suction machine 1 day before and 1 day after spraying.

BPH populations after the first

insecticide application differed significantly between treatments (see table). The most effective insecticides were carbofuran, MIPC, MTMC, BPMC, monocrotophos, and carbaryl. Results of the second and third applications were similar to those of the first.

Carbofuran gave the highest grain yield, followed by monocrotophos. Carbaryl gave lower yields than MIPC, MTMC, or BPMC. ■

Effectiveness of insecticides applied as foliar sprays against the brown planthopper (BPH) in central Thailand, 1977.

Treatment ^a	Formulation	BPH population ^b						Yield (t/ha)
		1st application (40DT)		2nd application (50DT)		3d application (70DT)		
		DBT	DAT	DBT	DAT	DBT	DAT	
Carbofuran	2F	1,271 a	15 a	144 a	19 a	149 ab	3 a	1.7 a
MIPC	50 WP	1,155 a	43 a	579 b	52 a	89 a	1 a	0.9 bc
MTMC	50 WP	1,875 bc	38 a	51 a	21 a	94 a	1 a	1.1 b
BPMC	50 WP	1,595 b	16 a	142 a	26 a	108 a	2 a	1.0 b
Monocrotophos	56 WSC	1,365 ab	413 b	195 b	185 b	214 bc	5 ab	1.3 ab
Carbaryl	85 WP	1,909 c	41 a	336 b	217 b	374 c	13 b	0.7 c
Control	-	2,184 d	1,215 c	751 b	1,229 c	417 c	154 c	0.2 d

^aApplied at 0.1% concentration.

^bAdults and nymphs from 4 replications.

DT = days after transplanting, DBT = days before treatment, DAT = days after treatment.

Means in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Soil and crop management

An easy mass-multiplication method for blue-green algae

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Commendable field experiments on the use of blue-green algae (equal to 25–30 kg N/ha) for higher rice yields have been conducted in various agroclimatic regions of India. Once the

yield-increasing effects of algal inoculation are better recognized, large-scale production of algal inoculum becomes important — at least in areas with favorable conditions. Until now, algae have been multiplied in concrete tanks or metal troughs, which require high initial expenditures that marginal farmers cannot afford.

Because the merit of such a device lies in the farmers' adoption of methods of preparing their own inoculum, experiments were conducted at the Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai, to develop a suitable multiplication technique. In 1978 a simple and easy method for mass multiplication of blue-green algae was standardized by